

Development of a Laser Resonance Ionization Scheme for Lead Using Titanium Sapphire Lasers for Radioactive Isotope Delivery at the TRIUMF ARIEL Facility

Entwicklung eines Laserresonanzionisationsschemas für Blei unter Verwendung von Titan-Saphir Lasern für die Bereitstellung radioaktiver Isotope in der TRIUMF ARIEL Anlage

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J. Wessolek

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1 Introduction

In Isotope Separator On-Line (ISOL) facilities all over the world, Radioactive Ion Beams (RIB) of a multitude of different isotopes are produced and made accessible to researchers to conduct experiments, reaching from atomic physics over nuclear physics to life sciences, material sciences and many more. Especially studies of exotic isotopes in regions far from stability give new insights in nuclear structure and nuclear astrophysics. In these regions, production rates are often low which makes Resonant Ionization Laser Ion Sources (RILIS) a popular tool to increase RIB intensity and purity. This gives rise to the need of efficient resonant ionization schemes that are feasible with the laser system at hand, which at TRIUMF, Canada's particle accelerator centre, is based on titanium sapphire (TiSa) lasers. For this thesis, TiSa laser based laser resonance ionization spectroscopy on lead was conducted to find an efficient ionization scheme that can be used in the on-line delivery of lead isotopes with TiSa laser based laser ion source.

1.1 Radioactive Ion Beam Production at TRIUMF ISAC

The main accelerator at TRIUMF is its cyclotron producing the primary proton beams. It accelerates H^- -ions to variable energies of up to 520 MeV, corresponding to a velocity of $\sim 0.75 c$, in a high frequency alternating electric field. A 4000-tonne six-sector magnet bends the ions on a trajectory spiralling outwards, where both of the electrons are stripped from the proton by thin foils of pyrolytic graphite. The proton is then deflected in the magnetic field, coupled out of the cyclotron and steered into one of four different beam lines. One of the beam lines, BL2A, guides a proton beam of up to 100 μA onto one of the two target stations of TRIUMF's Isotope Separator and Accelerator (ISAC). Through spallation, fragmentation and fission of the target nuclei, large areas of the nuclear chart are populated. Most frequently used are targets made out of stacks of D-shaped tantalum foils, but the use of targets made of other refractory materials like uranium carbide, silicon

carbide, niobium and uranium oxide is possible. The produced isotopes are stopped in the target, diffuse to the surface of the target material and then effuse into the transfer tube of the ion source, where they are ionized and extracted as an ion beam, mass separated and, if needed, post accelerated. The radioactive ion beam intensity available to experiments can be defined as the product of the following key parameters:

$$I_{RIB} = \Phi \sigma N_{target} \epsilon, \quad (1.1)$$

with Φ the proton beam intensity, σ the reaction cross section, N_{target} the amount of target atoms per surface area and ϵ is the total efficiency, which can be further described as the product of the efficiencies of three different processes:

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{release} \cdot \epsilon_{ionization} \cdot \epsilon_{transport}. \quad (1.2)$$

$\epsilon_{release}$ is the efficiency for the release of a certain isotope from the target and for its effusion into the ionizer. It is governed by the target temperature, which is typically around 2000 K, and the target's ratio of the bulk- to surface area. Release times of the atoms are in the order of seconds to minutes, but can be as high as hours or even infinite for refractory metals, which condense in the target even at these high temperatures.

$\epsilon_{ionization}$ is measure for how efficiently the atom is then ionized. Maximizing this value for as many different elements as possible is one of the main goals of TRIUMF's Resonant Ionization Laser Ion Source (TRILIS).

$\epsilon_{transport}$ describes the efficiency of the RIB transport from the ion source to the experiment and lies approximately between 50 % and 70 %.

The ionization can be done in three different ways:

Surface Ionization

Surface ionization is the process of ion formation in the desorption process from surfaces. Atoms are first adsorbed on a hot surface and can lose an electron when they desorb. The likelihood of ionization is highly dependant on the work function and temperature of the surface, and the ionization potential (IP) of the atoms. Therefore, it works best for elements with a rather low IP, like alkali- and alkaline earth metals. The surface ion source (SIS) at ISAC has a simple and rigid design, as it consists of only a hot tantalum tube of 3 mm diameter with a thin Rhenium foil liner. Due to the nature of the process, a surface ion source is not particularly element selective. In a mass separator, the produced ion beam is cleaned and only ions with a specific mass over charge ratio are transmitted. This blocks a major part of the unwanted isotopes but does not prevent isobaric contamination,

which is the contamination of a RIB with particles of similar mass as the requested isotope, but different proton and neutron numbers. To prevent this contamination, resonant laser ionization can be used instead of surface ionization.

Resonant Laser Ionization

The most suitable method to selectively ionize elements with an IP between 5 eV and 9.5 eV is multistep photoionization. Lead falls into that range with $IP_{Pb} = 7.42$ eV. The atoms are resonantly excited to an intermediate electronic state in one or more photoexcitation steps and then ionized in one of three ways: Nonresonantly, via a Rydberg state or through a resonance beyond the ionization potential, a so called autoionizing state. These three methods are covered in depth in subsection 2.1.2. Since the excitation to the intermediate state is resonant, only modest laser powers are needed to saturate these transitions. Therefore, the ionization step usually is the bottle neck of the ionization scheme. The excitation schemes of different elements are very distinct, which leads to great overall selectivity. $\epsilon_{ionization}$ of more than 20% have been achieved. During normal operation, resonant laser ionization is done inside the hot transfer tube of the surface ion source. Other elements with low IP are therefore still surface ionized, which can lead to isobaric contamination.

Figure 1.1: A schematic drawing of the ion guide laser ion source (IG-LIS). The surface ions are repelled by the red electrode and only the blue neutral atoms can reach the quadrupole ion guide, where they get laser ionized. Adapted from [1].

To produce isobar free RIBs, surface ionization must be suppressed. This can be done with the ion guide laser ion source (IG-LIS), which is schematically shown in Figure 1.1. It has a shorter transfer tube and a repeller electrode at the end to push surface ions back. Only neutral atoms can reach the ionization region, a radio frequency quadrupole ion guide. They then get ionized by the laser radiation and the ions can be extracted. The IG-LIS reduces contamination by up to six orders of magnitude, but the yield of the targeted ion also drops by a factor of ~ 50 . In [2], a more detailed description of the IG-LIS can be found.

Due to the laser system being far from high radiation areas, it can be serviced during target irradiation. It is located in a separate room next to the ISAC I experimental hall. The laser beams are transported down to the mass separator room and from there focused through a window in the pre-separator vacuum system into the transfer tube of the ion source. A distance of ~ 20 m is covered and six individual beams can be transported. Concrete shielding of the target and pre-separator magnet enables personnel access to the optics in the mass separator room when the proton beam is off. [3]

Forced Electron Beam Induced Arc Discharge (FEBIAD)

The FEBIAD ion source ionizes all elements, but only with efficiencies of $\epsilon_{ionization} \sim 10\%$, which is lower than SIS and TRILIS. The high isobaric background is undesirable. Thus this technique is only used for elements with high IPs that can not be ionized in a different way, like noble gases and halogens. [4]

1.2 Advanced Rare Isotope Laboratory (ARIEL)

With the new Advanced Rare IsotopE Laboratory (ARIEL), currently being constructed, the production of radioactive ion beams at TRIUMF will grow further. In its final stage, ARIEL will provide two additional radioactive ion beams (RIB), tripling TRIUMF's scientific output. One of the new beams will be driven by the protons of the main cyclotron, comparable to the existing RIB production at ISAC. The second beam will be driven by an electron beam, produced in an electron linear accelerator (e-linac). It consists of a 300 keV 10 mA electron gun, an injector cryomodule with elliptical superconducting RF cavities, and one accelerator cryomodule, also housing elliptical superconducting RF cavities. With that, beam energies of 30 MeV will be reached. Adding a second accelerator module

is planned, boosting the energy up to 50 MeV. The radioactive isotopes are produced by photo-induced fission of actinide targets. With that, intense beams of neutron rich isotopes can be delivered, without proton induced spallation by-products. Understanding the nuclear structure of neutron rich isotopes is a key to shed light onto the r-process and to understand the production of heavy elements in the universe. [5]

A laser laboratory in the ARIEL building will be home of the laser system of the new ARIEL laser ion source, providing laser beams for the two target stations. Additionally, enough space will be available for laser development and the off-line search for new ionization schemes.

1.3 Lead

Lead is a post transition metal of the carbon group, meaning it has four electrons in its outer shell. With an atomic number of $Z = 82$, it is the heaviest element with stable isotopes. Their masses and relative abundances are shown in Table 1.1. Precise atomic masses are measured with penning trap mass spectrometers, such as the TITAN penning trap at TRIUMF, that seeks to extend precision mass measurements to radioactive isotopes [6].

Isotope	Mass	Abundance
^{204}Pb	203.973	1.4%
^{206}Pb	205.974	24.1%
^{207}Pb	206.976	22.1%
^{208}Pb	207.977	52.4%

Table 1.1: The four stable isotopes of lead with their atomic masses and relative natural abundances.

Lead acts as a neurotoxin. Exposure to lead mainly results from inhalation and ingestion of lead particles. Occupational and environmental sources are for example smelting, stripping of lead paint, water from leaded pipes and lead-soldered food containers. Leaded gasoline has been responsible for $\sim 90\%$ of human lead exposure. Today, more than $3/4$ of the lead intake is due to the manufacturing of lead-acid batteries. According to the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME), lead exposure accounted for an estimated 1.06 million deaths worldwide in 2017 [7].

An efficient ionization scheme for lead can help with trace detection and monitoring

public health risks. To minimize the lead exposure of TRIUMF employees, the TRIUMF site underwent a clean-up in which all lead shielding bricks not painted as required were removed and areas contaminated underwent dust removal.

The abundance of the different lead isotopes can be used to date rock samples. ^{206}Pb , ^{207}Pb and ^{208}Pb are the final products of decay chains starting from ^{238}U , ^{235}U and ^{232}Th , respectively. ^{204}Pb is the only non-radiogenic isotope of lead. Uranium-lead dating is usually applied to zircon. During formation, this mineral integrates uranium and thorium atoms into its structure. Lead atoms however are strongly rejected. Because the half-lives of the three decay routes are well known, one can determine the age of the sample by measuring the current ratios of $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$, $^{235}\text{U}/^{207}\text{Pb}$ or $^{232}\text{Th}/^{208}\text{Pb}$. The relative uncertainties of this method are usually below one percent [8].

Due to the different decay channels, the age of rocks can also be determined by analysing the lead isotope ratios alone. With this lead-lead dating method, the age of several different meteorites and the earth itself was measured to be $(4.55 \pm 0.05) \times 10^9$ years in 1956 [9]. Laser resonance ionization is also used for such isotope ratio determinations in geochemistry, cosmology and environmental sciences [10].

2 Theory

2.1 Resonant Laser Ionization

In this section, the principles of resonant laser ionisation are described. The standard textbooks on this topic are by Hurst and Payne [11] and Letokhov [12]. Also, a discussion of different possible ionization schemes for lead is given.

2.1.1 Selection Rules

Every element has a characteristic energy level structure. A quantum mechanical approach to a bound particle, like an electron in the Coulomb field of a nucleus, shows that such a particle can only be present in distinct states $|i\rangle$ with corresponding energies E_i . An atom can be excited into higher states by absorbing a photon with energy $h\nu_{ik}$ corresponding to the energy difference of a lower initial state $|i\rangle$ and an excited final state $|k\rangle$:

$$\Delta E = E_k - E_i = h\nu_{ik}. \quad (2.1)$$

The electronic state of a one electron atom is fully characterized by a set of four quantum numbers $nlm_l m_s$. n is the principal quantum number and can have positive integers as its value. The orbital angular momentum l can take on positive integers and zero, and has $n - 1$ as an upper limit. In the spectroscopic notation, every value of l is represented by a letter: 0:s, 1:p, 2:d, 3:f and from there on alphabetically. m_l and m_s , the magnetic quantum numbers, describe the projection of l and the electron spin s on an arbitrarily chosen direction, conventionally called the z -axis of the atom, and can have integer values from $-l$ to l and $-s$ to s , respectively. In the case of one electron, $s = 1/2$ and $m_s = \pm 1/2$. The conservation of angular momentum gives rise to certain selection rules for optical transitions:

Due to the photon's angular momentum of \hbar , electric dipole transitions are only allowed when

$$\Delta l = \pm 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta s = 0. \quad (2.2)$$

In light multielectron atoms, all orbital momenta couple to $\vec{L} = \sum_i \vec{l}_i$, all spins couple to $\vec{S} = \sum_i \vec{s}_i$ and $\vec{J} = \vec{L} + \vec{S}$. This is called LS -coupling and analogous to Equation 2.2, $\Delta L = \pm 1$ and $\Delta S = 0$ must be fulfilled. In heavy multi electron atoms like lead, each electron's spin and orbit couple to $\vec{j}_i = \vec{l}_i + \vec{s}_i$ and all \vec{j}_i couple to

$$\vec{J} = \sum_i \vec{j}_i. \quad (2.3)$$

This is called jj -coupling. The selection rules stated for LS -coupling are no longer valid and a transition must fulfill

$$\Delta J = 0, \pm 1 \quad \text{and} \quad J = 0 \rightarrow J = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

The ground state of lead in jj -coupling is $6p^2 \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right)_0$. This means that the two outer electrons are in the p-shell and have therefore an orbital angular momentum of $l = 1$. The spin of both electrons is $s = 1/2$. For each electron, these two momenta couple to $j_i = 1/2$, shown in parenthesis. The j_i then couple to a total angular momentum of $J = 0$, represented by the index 0.

Depending on the polarization of the absorbed light, the magnetic quantum number M_J has to change:

$$\Delta M_J = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad \pi \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta M_J = \pm 1 \quad \text{for} \quad \sigma^\pm \quad (2.5)$$

If $\Delta J = 0$, transitions from $M_{J,i} = 0$ to $M_{J,k} = 0$ are forbidden. The laser light used at TRILIS is linearly polarized and the light of different excitation steps is usually parallel to each other

Another often used coupling scheme in literature is j_1K -coupling. Here, j_1 is same as in jj -coupling. The orbital angular momentum of the excited electron couples with j_1 to form the new quantum number K , which then couples with the spin of the excited electron to the total angular momentum J . The $6p \ 7p \left(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right)_2$ level of lead would in j_1K -coupling be $6p \ 7p \left[\frac{5}{2}\right]_2$, where j_1 couples with l_2 to $K = 5/2$, coupling with the spin to $J = 2$ [13, 14].

A detailed description of the different coupling schemes can be found in the NIST Atomic Spectroscopy Compendium [13].

2.1.2 Ionization

As briefly described in section 1.1, the final step of an ionization scheme, the ionization step, can usually be done in one of three different manners, as shown in Figure 2.1:

Figure 2.1: The three different methods of laser-ionizing an atom, here shown as three step schemes without loss of generality.

Nonresonant Ionization into the Continuum

Nonresonant ionization into the continuum is the most straightforward method of laser ionization. The only condition that has to be fulfilled is that the photon energy is at least as high as the energy difference from the last intermediate level $|i\rangle$ to the IP

$$h\nu \geq IP - E_i. \quad (2.6)$$

With larger difference to the IP, the cross section shrinks drastically, so for $h\nu = IP - E_i$ it has its maximum [15]. When the laser power is constant, the number of photons sinks with increasing photon energy, which also lowers the probability of ionization. Typical cross sections are in the order of $\sigma \sim (10^{-19} - 10^{-17}) \text{ cm}^2$ [16].

Resonant Ionization via an Autoionizing Resonance

An autoionizing state is a simultaneous excitation of two electrons. It can either decay by sending out two photons, or one electron relaxes which increases the screening of the valence electron from the nucleus. This reduces the binding energy and the valence

electron is no longer bound. The inner core remains as ion. Cross sections are $\sigma \sim (10^{-16} - 10^{-15}) \text{ cm}^2$, but can be as high as 10^{-12} cm^2 . Due to their very short lifetimes, most autoionizing states have large natural linewidths of $\Delta\nu > 100 \text{ GHz}$ [15, 17, 18], but some elements have very narrow AI lines, like gadolinium [19].

Ionization out of a Rydberg State

Exciting an electron into a Rydberg state is also an efficient way to ionize an atom [11]. The required energy to cross the IP is then provided by an external electric field in the ionizer, thermal radiation or collisions with other atoms. Cross sections are in the order of $\sigma \sim 10^{-14} \text{ cm}^2$ [20].

The energies of the Rydberg states of a specific series follow the Rydberg formula

$$E_n = IP - \frac{Ry^*}{(n - \delta_{nl})^2} = IP - \frac{Ry^*}{n^{*2}}, \quad (2.7)$$

with E_n the energy of the Rydberg state with principal quantum number n , Ry^* the element specific reduced mass Rydberg constant, for ^{208}Pb $109\,737.0262 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and δ_{nl} the quantum defect. n and δ are often combined to an efficient quantum number n^* . The quantum defect is a shielding constant and a measure for how much the core electrons shield the Rydberg electron from interaction with the nucleus. Its dependency on n can be neglected for large n . If n is not sufficiently large, the quantum defect can be expanded into a series, the Ritz expansion:

$$\delta(n) = \delta_0 + \frac{a}{(n - \delta_0)^2} + \frac{b}{(n - \delta_0)^4} + \mathcal{O}(n^6) \quad (2.8)$$

The Rydberg series converges against an energy limit called the ionization potential

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_n = IP. \quad (2.9)$$

2.1.3 Broadening Mechanisms and Line Shapes

An excited state $|k\rangle$ has a lifetime τ_k . Due to the uncertainty principle, a natural linewidth $\Delta\nu_k$ arises:

$$\frac{h}{2\pi} \leq \Delta E_k \tau_k = h \Delta\nu_k \tau_k \quad (2.10)$$

$$\Rightarrow \Delta\nu_k \geq \frac{1}{2\pi\tau_k}. \quad (2.11)$$

A state with a short lifetime will have a large energy uncertainty and therefore a broad linewidth. The resulting line profile is Lorentzian, because the broadening affects all atoms equally.

If an atom moves relative to an incoming photon, the frequency of that photon is shifted in the reference frame of the atom, depending on its velocity and direction. This is due to the Doppler effect. At high temperatures and under low pressures, an ensemble of atoms approximately behaves like an ideal gas. Its velocity distribution is then described by the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, which depends on the atoms temperature [21]. This results in a temperature dependant broadening of the linewidth, the Doppler broadening, with linewidth

$$\Delta\nu_D = \nu_0 \sqrt{\frac{8k_B T \ln(2)}{mc^2}}, \quad (2.12)$$

where ν_0 is the rest frequency, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, m is the atoms mass and c the speed of light. Since this broadening effect is inhomogeneous, the resulting line shape is gaussian. For the most abundant lead isotope ^{208}Pb and the first excitation step with $\lambda = 283.389 \text{ nm}$, that leads to a Doppler width of $\Delta\nu_D = 1.65 \text{ GHz}$ at 1000 K. This is much broader than the natural linewidth, which can be calculated from the transitions Einstein coefficient to $\Delta\nu_n = A/2\pi = 4.9 \times 10^7 \text{ s}^{-1}/2\pi = 7.8 \text{ MHz}$.

The TiSa lasers of TRILIS have a linewidth of about 1 GHz - 10 GHz, depending on the laser optics and output wavelength, and therefore have a good spectral overlap with the Doppler broadened lines [22].

Autoionizing levels often have asymmetric line shapes. This so-called Fano profile is due to the interference between the nonresonant ionization process into the continuum and the resonant excitation into the autoionizing level [23].

2.2 Laser System

To search for ionization schemes, the laser system needs a large tuning range, so transitions in different elements can be excited. It also needs to be scannable to search for Rydberg states and autoionizing states. For stability, simplicity and wide tuning range, the TRILIS laser system is based exclusively on solid state titanium sapphire lasers.

2.2.1 Pulsed nanosecond Titanium Sapphire Lasers

The active medium of a titanium sapphire (TiSa) laser is a sapphire crystal (Al_2O_3), in which some of the Al^{3+} -ions have been replaced by Ti^{3+} -ions.

Sapphire as host material has an excellent thermal conductivity, obviating thermal effects even at high laser powers and intensities. The Ti^{3+} 's bandwidth is large, allowing the required tunability. The emission maximum lays around 800 nm, but laser operation from 660 nm to 1000 nm is possible. The absorption peaks at ~ 490 nm, but no powerful laser diodes are available at that wavelength to be used for pumping the TiSa crystal. This is nowadays usually done with a frequency doubled Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm. In the TRILIS off-line laser system, a Q-switched frequency doubled Nd:YAG¹ is used. Its power can be divided with the help of waveplates and polarizing beam splitter cubes to pump several TiSa lasers. The absorption and emission spectrum of a TiSa crystal can be seen in Figure 2.2.

¹Continuum Mesa 532-40L, frequency doubled Nd:YAG laser

Figure 2.2: The absorption and emission spectrum of a TiSa crystal. The absorption at 532 nm is large enough to pump TiSa lasers relatively efficient with widely available frequency doubled Nd:YAG lasers. The broad emission spectrum allows laser operation from 660 nm to 990 nm, making TiSa lasers with additional frequency conversion suitable for resonant laser ionization. Figure from [24].

To achieve a good crystal quality, the concentration of Ti^{3+} -ions has to be low, typically around 0.1 %. That limits the pump absorption and leads to crystals of several mm in length.

The resonator design of the TRILIS TiSa lasers is based on a TiSa laser from Johannes Gutenberg University in Mainz, Germany [25] and the cw tunable TiSa laser design by Spectra Physics, S3900. It works at repetition rates of 10 kHz and is suitable for laser ionisation due to high pulse peak powers, so that even weak transitions can be saturated and eventual frequency conversion has a high efficiency. The resonator is Z-shaped and the angles are chosen in a way that corrects any astigmatism of the TiSa crystal's surfaces. Except for the mirrors, all optical elements are passed under Brewster angle to minimize losses. The high reflectors and the two curved mirrors have reflectivities close to 100 % at their center wavelength and the output coupler has $R \sim 80\%$, which fits well for pulsed operation at 10 kHz. The TRILIS TiSa lasers average output powers of more than 1 W in the wavelength region of 680 nm to 990 nm when pumped with 10 W at 532 nm.

2.2.2 Pockels Cell for Pulse Synchronisation

To synchronize the pulse trains of the different lasers, the resonators are equipped with Pockels cells. A Pockels cell acts as a Q-switch and is based on the electro-optical effect rotating the polarization of light [16]. When a high voltage applied to, a potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP) crystal acts like a retardation plate and changes the polarization direction of the passing light as a function of that voltage. With that, additional losses can be introduced to the cavity with a number of Brewster surfaces. Lowering these losses at the right time by changing the voltage triggers a laser pulse build-up and pulse release, so that synchronous operation can be achieved [26].

2.2.3 Wavelength Selection

To select the desired wavelength from the TiSa's emission spectrum, wavelength-selective elements are added to the resonator. For the lasers driving the excitations to intermediate levels, this is done with a birefringent filter (BRF) and a thin Fabry-Perot etalon. A schematic drawing of that can be found in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: A schematic drawing of the TiSa laser with birefringent filter and thin etalon as wavelength selective elements [27].

The BRF consists of four birefringent plates of different thickness. They change the light's polarization from linear to elliptical depending on the wavelength and the angle of the

filter. Due to the Brewster surfaces in the cavity, s-polarization is suppressed. This leads to a cosine squared transmission profile for each plate of the BRF, each with a different thickness and therefore a different period. Multiplying the different transmission profiles gives a curve with relatively sharp peak and a broad free spectral range (FSR), as seen in Figure 2.4. Turning the filter shifts the transmission curve. To prevent the TiSa from lasing in a peak near its emission maximum, a suitable set of mirrors with sufficient losses for said wavelength and high reflectivity for the requested wavelength must be used. The BRF leads to a linewidth of about 100 GHz.

Figure 2.4: The transmission profile of the different plates of the multi-plate BRF, thicknesses from top to bottom 0.5 mm, 1.5 mm, 3 mm, 6 mm and the transmission of the combination of all plates on the bottom. It can be seen that the free spectral range is determined by the thinnest plate, whereas the width of the transition peak depends on the thickest plate.

To further narrow that linewidth, a thin etalon can be used. It consists of a thin glass plate which is coated on both sides for higher reflectivity and only transmits wavelengths that interfere constructively with themselves after one internal round trip (two internal reflections). The optical path length, and therefore the transmitted wavelength, can be selected by tilting the etalon. The resulting linewidth is usually around $\Delta\nu \approx 4$ GHz [26]. If required, also multiple solid etalons can be used.

The scanning laser for the ionization step has a blazed diffraction grating² for wavelength selection, shown in Figure 2.5. It is built in Littrow configuration, so turning the grating changes the wavelength fed back into the resonator and therefore selects the output wavelength of the TiSa laser. An alternative to that would be the Littman-Metcalf configuration, where the grating is fixed and an additional mirror is rotated around it to reflect the requested wavelength. Due to the lower output efficiency of this setup, the Littrow configuration is used in our laser. This allows to scan the laser wavelength. The grating is mounted on a rotary stage³ with a resolution of $0.87 \mu\text{rad}$, corresponding to a tuning accuracy of about 0.5 GHz. The rotation stage used can be controlled with a PC. To achieve a narrow linewidth, a beam expander is used to illuminate as many grooves of the grating as possible. The expander consists of two anamorphic prism pairs made of SF11, giving a one dimensional beam expansion by a factor of ~ 10 -17. Also, this reduces the energy density on the grating's gold coating and therefore prevents damaging the grating. To further reduce the light intensity on the grating, a partial reflector with $R \sim 50\%$ is used in front of the beam expander [28]. The linewidth of the grating laser is $\Delta\nu \approx 7 \text{ GHz}$ [26].

Figure 2.5: A schematic drawing of the TiSa laser with a diffractive grating as wavelength selective element. The grating can be turned remotely to scan a broad wavelength range in the search for Rydberg states and autoionizing states. [28]

²Newport 53-108ZD02-290R, Richardson diffraction grating, 1800 mm^{-1} , blaze at 500 nm

³Aerotech ADRS-100, rotary stage, resolution $0.87 \mu\text{rad}$

The wavelengths are monitored to a precision of 10^{-6} with a wavemeter⁴, calibrated by a polarization stabilized helium neon laser⁵.

2.2.4 Harmonic Frequency Generation

The first excitation step in lead is in the ultra violet at $\lambda = 283.389$ nm, which can not be reached by the TiSa's NIR emission. This makes harmonic frequency generation necessary. The polarisation density $\vec{P}(t)$ of a medium evoked by the electric field $\vec{E}(t)$ can be described by a Taylor series

$$\vec{P}(t) = \epsilon_0 \left(\chi^{(1)} \vec{E}(t) + \chi^{(2)} \vec{E}^2(t) + \dots \right) \quad (2.13)$$

with ϵ_0 the electric permittivity of the vacuum and $\chi^{(n)}$ the n-th order susceptibility. The second order term describes a three-wave mixing processes and therefore second-harmonic generation and sum-frequency generation. Two photons with frequencies ν_1 and ν_2 get converted to one photon with $\nu_3 = \nu_1 + \nu_2$ [29].

Due to chromatic dispersion, the propagation velocities of the fundamental and second harmonic in the non-linear medium are not equal. A constant phase relation between them is needed, so that all photons of the second harmonic interfere constructively, independently of where in the medium they are produced. To achieve this phase matching, a birefringent crystal is used. TRILIS uses beta-barium borate (BBO) crystals and type-I phase matching, in which the fundamental waves travel as extraordinary waves and the second harmonic as ordinary. The angle of the crystal is now chosen in such a way that both waves see the same index of refraction which leads to the required constructive interference. The efficiency of second order processes is proportional to E^2 , so the high intensities of the pulsed TRILIS lasers are well suited. For frequency doubling, efficiencies around 10 % - 20% are achieved at TRILIS with the aforementioned 10 W pump power. Tripling and quadrupling reach efficiencies of 1 % - 2 %.

2.2.5 Laser for Nonresonant Ionization

If the ionization is done nonresonantly, the laser powers to saturate such a step exceed what the TiSa lasers can provide. Therefore, a diode pumped Nd:YVO₄ laser⁶ is used for

⁴High Finesse Angstrom WS/6 wavemeter, 600 MHz absolute accuracy

⁵Melles Griot 05 STP 901/903, helium neon laser, frequency stability ± 2 MHz/8 h

⁶Spectra Physics YHP 40 Navigator II, diode pumped Nd:YVO₄ laser

that. At 1064 nm, the system available has an output power of 13 W. For ionization steps, that exceed the 1064 nm photon's energy, a doubling unit can be added to the laser, so it provides light at 532 nm with a power of up to 6.7 W. The good beam profile of $M^2 < 1.2$ results in high focus intensities and therefore a good ionization efficiency [30]. Also, its pulse length of ~ 30 ns matches the TiSa's pulse lengths well.

2.3 Mass Filtering and Ion Detection

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer

In the quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS), a radio frequency (RF) quadrupole acts as a bandpass filter, letting only ions with a specific mass over charge ratio pass through to the detector. By tuning the applied voltages, the position of the bandpass can be changed and a mass spectrum can be recorded.

In contrast to mass separator magnets and time-of-flight spectrometers, quadrupoles resolve directly on the mass over charge ratio and therefore mostly independent from velocity- or momentum spread of the ion beam. The instrument is also of great mechanical simplicity: It consists of four rod electrodes with hyperbolic cross section in a square layout along the ion flight axis (z-axis). As shown in [31], the best approximation of a quadrupole field with rods of circular cross section is achieved for $r = 1.1486r_0$, with r the radius of the electrodes and $2r_0$ the distance between the surfaces of two opposing rods. The filtering is obtained by driving the electrodes with an RF-voltage and a constant voltage offset.

In the following, the motion of positively charged ions is qualitatively described for the x-z and y-z planes separately, as laid out in [32]. For a more rigorous approach, see [33]. In the x-z plane, during the first half of one period of the RF-voltage, the ions experience a positive potential and are focused onto the z-axis. In the second half, they are defocused by the negative potential. If an ion hits one of the negative electrodes and therefore does not make it to the detector, depends on several factors, including frequency and magnitude of the RF-voltage and position, velocity and mass over charge ratio of the particle.

Now, a constant positive potential is added to the RF-term. A heavy ion will not follow the RF-potential as quickly and will only be affected by the positive constant potential and therefore be focused onto the z-axis. A light ion will feel a considerable effect of the RF-potential to a point where the acceleration away from the z-axis during the negative potential is high enough for it to strike an electrode. In the x-direction, the QMS therefore acts as a high pass mass filter, only transmitting ions above a certain mass over charge

value.

The potential in y-direction has the same magnitude as the one in x-direction, only with an opposite sign. For the RF-term, it only shifts the phase by 180 deg. The constant negative potential however defocuses heavy ions, because their motion can not follow the RF-potential. Light ions are focused enough by the positive part of the RF-potential so that their trajectories are stable. In the y-direction, the QMS acts as a low pass mass filter. Only ions that are stable in both planes can travel through the whole quadrupole. The width of the bandpass, which is the mass resolution, depends on the ratio of the RF-voltage to the constant voltage offset.

The solutions of the Mathieu equation can be studied graphically. The stability of the solutions and therefore the stability of the ion's trajectories in the quadrupole depend on the parameters a and q . This is best shown on an $a - q$ stability diagram in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: $a - q$ stability diagram of the solutions of the Mathieu equation. The shaded area corresponds to stable solutions in both the x- and y-direction. [34]

The shaded area corresponds to stable solutions in both the x- and y-direction. To scan the transmitted mass, the magnitude of RF- and directed current are varied, while their ratio is held constant. By that, the position of the stable region is scanned along the mass scan line. The slope of the mass scan line is given by $2U/V$. With a steeper mass scan line, the size of the intersection with the region of stability decreases, which leads to a higher mass resolution. Downstream of the quadrupole mass spectrometer, the LIS STAND uses a channel electron multiplier to detect the ions to record the mass spectra. The LIS STAND also has several Faraday cups for beam diagnostics. Their operating principles are briefly described below.

Channel Electron Multiplier

Figure 2.7: A schematic drawing of a CEM tube. The primary radiation starts an avalanche of secondary electrons. The current pulse is then measured at the tubes output. [35]

Figure 2.8: A CEM with a conversion dynode. An incoming ion is accelerated by a high negative bias of the dynode and produces several electrons on impact. The electrons are then accelerated to the channels input, further multiplied and detected. [35]

Channel electron multipliers (CEM) are widely used in mass spectrometry applications. They consist of a bent glass funnel with a semiconducting layer on the inside acting as a continuous dynode. Figure 2.7 shows, how incoming primary radiation striking the input produces 2-3 electrons which are accelerated down the channel by a positive bias. They hit the walls repeatedly which results in a pulse of up to 10^8 electrons at the output end. Through that, CEMs can detect single particles with count rates of up to $\sim 10^6\text{s}^{-1}$. Through bending the funnel, ion feedback is prevented. Any ions produced at the output through electron collisions with residual gas atoms can not travel up the channel and trigger an avalanche of secondary electrons and with it a false signal, but collide with the wall before they can gain enough energy to produce any electrons. To prevent the CEM from surface damage (sputtering) through direct heavy ion impact, a negatively biased conversion dynode can be used, as seen in Figure 2.8. An incoming ion is accelerated by a high negative bias of the dynode and produces several electrons on impact. The electrons are then accelerated to the channels input, further multiplied and detected [35].

Faraday Cup

A Faraday cup (FC) is a conductive cup designed to detect charged particles. When an ion hits the cup, its charge is transferred to the FC on neutralization of the ion. The cup is part of a circuit with an electrometer. The flowing current that is directly proportional to the number of incoming charged particles can be measured very accurately down to a fA level [36].

At TRIUMF, Faraday cups are used for ion beam diagnosis at many points in the different beam lines.

3 Development of a Suitable Ionization Scheme for Lead

3.1 Laser Ion Source Test Stand (LIS STAND)

It is practical and necessary to perform the development of resonant laser ionization schemes for the stable isotopes of different elements in an off-line test facility. In this way, the development does not interfere with on-line RIB production and the costs are reduced. The so found schemes can then be applied on-line to ionize radioactive isotopes efficiently. At TRIUMF, a compact test stand (LIS STAND) was built to fulfill this task [26]. A cross section of the test stand is shown in Figure 3.1. To assure direct transfer from off-line results to on-line operation, the ion source and extraction optics are a copy of those used on-line. The LIS STAND can operate at ion beam energies of up to 35 keV, which is a typical beam energy used on-line. A high through put quadrupole mass spectrometer¹ is used as a mass spectrometer. It offers fast mass scans at a variable resolution R , that depends on the number of cycles n of the RF voltage, the ion sees while passing through the quadrupole, and therefore on the energy E_{inj} of the ion. The resolution can be estimated by

$$n \approx \omega_{RF} L \sqrt{\frac{m}{2eE_{inj}}}, \quad (3.1)$$

$$R_{max} \approx \frac{n^2}{12.2}, \quad (3.2)$$

with ω_{RF} the RF frequency, L the length of the quadrupole structure and m the ion mass [37]. This gives a resolution of around $\frac{m}{\Delta m} \sim 115$ at the set ion energy of 70 eV. Also, the footprint and weight are small compared to a mass separator magnet. The QMS has rods of 19 mm diameter, driven with a RF voltage at 1.2 MHz. The mass scan range that can be achieved is $\frac{A}{q} = 2 - 300$.

¹ABB Extrel MAX-300, 1.2 MHz RF, 19 mm \varnothing rod system, 300amu quadrupole mass spectrometer

With lower ion beam energy, the mass resolution can be increased further. The system's deceleration optics are based on conical retardation electronics which are also applied at TITAN (TRIUMF's Ion Trap for Atomic and Nuclear Science) for injection into their RF ion cooler and buncher. Ion detection can be done in two different ways: For rates of up to $1 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$, a channel electron multiplier² is used. Ion currents from tenths of fA up to hundreds of nA are detected with a Faraday cup. A short explanation of the detector principles is given in section 2.3.

The vacuum system is about 2 m long and 3 m high. The main chamber with the ion source in it can be decoupled from the rest of the ion beam path by a gate valve and therefore be vented separately. That reduces the evacuation time after loading the ionizer with a new sample. The rough vacuum is established via two dry scroll pumps³. A 1000 L/s turbo molecular pump⁴ at the main chamber and a 500 L/s turbo molecular pump⁵ at the deflector chamber pump down the system to pressures typically below 1×10^{-6} Torr [20].

²DeTech 402A-H

³Varian Tri Scroll 300

⁴Varian V1001

⁵Varian V501

Figure 3.1: A sectional solidworks drawing of the LIS STAND. 1 - Source Chamber, 2 - Deflector, 3 - Beam Diagnostics, 4 - Deceleration Optics, 5 - Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer. [20]

The laser beams enter the test stand through a small wedged entry window in the deflector chamber. It is made of UV grade fused silica for the transmission of wavelengths between 200 nm – 2000 nm. The $\sim 4\%$ reflection from the window are viewed on a ceramic plate, which is positioned on the laser table in the same distance to the window as the ion source. This is used as a reference to monitor the overlap and focusing of the different laser beams. The ions are extracted from the ionizer and transported through a 3.4 m long flight path with Einzel lenses and parallel plate beam steerers. A spherical electrostatic deflector bends the beam 90° before it gets decelerated and enters the QMS. The ion transport efficiency ranges between 20 % and 30 %.

Figure 3.2: Temperature curve of the ion source in the LIS STAND. This curve is the average of several measurements taken with an optical pyrometer and a laser thermometer.

The ion source is usually operated at temperatures around 2000 K. A water-cooling system prevents various electrodes from malfunctions. A temperature curve was taken with an optical pyrometer⁶ and a laser thermometer⁷ and is shown in Figure 3.2. For heating currents lower than 160 A, the fluctuations in the laser thermometer reading were too large to continue the measurement. For the evaporation of lead, lower heating currents of 65 A and 75 A were used. One additional Rydberg scan with a higher heating current of 160 A was also conducted and is shown in Figure 3.8. To find the exact crucible temperature for lower heating currents, a thermocouple could be used. This would have the drawback of creating an additional heat sink, probably causing an uneven heat distribution in the source.

The whole LIS STAND is controlled through a virtual machine environment based on an Experimental Physics and Industry Computer System (EPICS). Soft- and hardware interlocks protect users and equipment from electrical hazards. For in detail description of the LIS STAND, please see J.-P. Lavois' PhD. Thesis [20].

⁶Hartmann & Braun Pyropto

⁷Omega iR2C

3.2 Spectroscopy of the Even Parity Rydberg Levels of Lead

A good starting point in the development of an efficient ionization scheme for resonant laser ionization of lead is a scan through the Rydberg levels. The wavelengths of the applied two step scheme are suitable for the TRILIS TiSa lasers at hand.

Figure 3.3: Scheme of two step ionization of lead. The first excitation step to the $6p7s(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_1^o$ level was achieved by a tripled TiSa laser at 283.389 nm, the excitation into the Rydberg levels was done by a doubled laser scanning from 453 nm to the ionization potential. Nonresonant 532 nm laser light was added to enhance the signal. A further scan from the IP down to 353 nm without the added 532 nm laser light did not show any autoionizing levels. Given energies are taken from the NIST atomic spectroscopy database [38]. All given wavelengths are vacuum wavelengths.

The experimental setup and beam transport is shown in Figure 3.4. All given wavelengths throughout this thesis are vacuum wavelengths. The first step wavelength of $\lambda_1 = 283.389 \text{ nm}$ excites the lead atoms from the $6p^2(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ ground level to the $6p7s(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_1^o$ level at $35287.225 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and is the usual first excitation step for lead, also used by [39–41].

Figure 3.4: Scheme of the experimental setup on the laser table for the two step ionization of lead. For the first excitation step, a BRF tuned TiSa laser with a fundamental wavelength of 850.166 nm was intracavity doubled and the fundamental, as well as the second harmonic, were focused into a BBO doubling crystal. This leads to the required $\lambda_1 = 283.389$ nm. The excitation into the Rydberg levels was done with a frequency doubled grating tuned TiSa laser, scanning wavelengths from 453 nm to 353 nm. To enhance the ionization out of the Rydberg levels and therefore enhance the signal to noise ratio, a doubled diode pumped Nd:YVO₄ laser was added.

In the birefringent filter tuned TiSa laser, tuned to a fundamental wavelength of 850.166 nm, generation of the second harmonic (SH) was done inside the cavity. The high intensities there make focusing into the BBO crystal unnecessary, which simplifies the setup and provides a near gaussian beam profile of the SH. A dichroic mirror reflecting the SH light and letting the fundamental pass, is used to keep the SH light out of the rest of the resonator and double the SH output intensity. Both the fundamental and the second harmonic were coupled out of the resonator and focused into another BBO crystal, which then emitted the required first step wavelength of 283.389 nm through type I sum frequency generation. For this, a dual wave $\lambda/2$ -plate was used to rotate the polarization direction of the SH by 90° for

third harmonic generation in the tripling crystal. The scanning through the Rydberg levels was achieved with a grating tuned TiSa laser. Frequency doubling was done outside of the cavity with a single pass of the focused beam through a doubling crystal. With changing wavelength, this crystal was rotated along the beam axis to adjust for the wavelength dependence of the phase matching angle. The resulting beam displacement was corrected by a beam lock system⁸ to ensure a stable overlap with the ionization region in the ion source. To support ionization from the Rydberg levels and therefore enhancing the ion current signal, light from a doubled diode pumped Nd:YVO₄ laser at 532 nm was added. The laser power was 11 mW for the first excitation step and 160 – 230 mW for the second step, depending on the wavelength. The doubled Nd:YVO₄ laser had an output power of 6.5 W. All three beams were expanded with telescopes to ensure a tight focus with small beam waist inside the ionizer tube. They were overlapped with dichroic mirrors and focused into the ionizer tube with a lens of 5 m focal length. The 2" mirror mounts⁹ used for beam overlap were equipped with 170 TPI adjustors for ease of alignment. As sample, a $\sim 4 \text{ mm}^2$ piece of lead foil of 0.0038 cm thickness was used. With a density of 11.35 g/cm^3 , that equals a mass of 1.7 mg. The lead was wrapped in a piece of tantalum foil to ensure slow and even release and put into the ionizer tube of the LIS STAND ion source. The water cooled heat shield was installed, the vacuum chamber was closed and pumped down to operating pressure.

⁸TEM Aligna

⁹LIOPTECH Star Series SR200 mirror mount

Figure 3.5: Photograph of the ion source inside the LIS STAND. The copper heat shield was disassembled. Marked with number 1 are the water cooled contacts of the heating current. The lead sample was placed inside the ionizer tube which is marked with the number 2.

The heating current applied to the crucible was 65 A. This was enough to evaporate lead atoms from the sample, probably supported by heating from the 532 nm laser. The CEM was used with an analog amplifier and ion signal gain was set to a factor of 10^9 . The counts in the mass range from 208 u to 208.01 u were summed up as ion current.

In this setup, Rydberg series with $J = 0, 2$ were expected for ^{208}Pb . Since the light of both excitation steps had linear polarization parallel to each other, only transitions with $\Delta M_J = 0$ were allowed. For a second step into a series with $J = 1$, ΔJ would be 0, but since M_J of both the initial and the final state is 0, this transition is forbidden.

This holds true only for isotopes with zero nuclear spin, like ^{208}Pb . For ^{207}Pb , $I = \frac{1}{2}$ and due to the coupling of nuclear spin and total angular momentum of the electrons, M_J is not a good quantum number anymore and a transition into a Rydberg series with $J = 1$ is possible. Since the mass resolution was less than unit resolution, the observed series with $J = 1$ most likely comes from the ionization of ^{207}Pb . Furthermore, if the polarization of the two resonant laser beams was not perfectly parallel, the perpendicular component of the second excitation step can be expressed as a combination of σ^+ and σ^- light in respect

to the quantization axis of the first excitation step. With this, transitions of $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ are allowed and a series with $J = 1$ would be possible for ^{208}Pb . A closer look at this polarization dependency effect is taken in [42]. In the development of an ionization scheme this has to be taken into account to ensure efficient ionization of all isotopes, independent of their nuclear momentum.

Figure 3.6: Spectrum of the two step ionization of lead via the $6p7s(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_1^{\circ}$ level. Four different Rydberg series were identified: The $6np(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ series, the $6np(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ series, the $6np(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ series and the $6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ series. These four series converge to the $6p_{1/2}$ ionization potential. In addition, three $6p7p$ perturber levels of series converging to the $6p_{3/2}$ limit were identified. Level assignments are from [39].

In Figure 3.6, the spectrum of the two step ionization of lead via the $6p7s(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_1^{\circ}$ level is shown. The scan was done in three parts on different days and the spectrum was later put together by connecting the different parts. Peaks in the overlapping regions of neighboring parts were used for normalization of the peak heights. This was done to account for slightly different laser powers and eventual differences in sample evaporation.

Four different Rydberg series were identified: The $6np(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ series for principal quan-

tum numbers of $11 \leq n \leq 35$, missing $n = 23$, the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ series for $11 \leq n \leq 25$, missing $n = 19, 20, 21, 23$, the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ series for $12 \leq n \leq 54$, missing $n = 23$, and the $6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ series for $8 \leq n \leq 31$, missing $n = 17, 20$. These four series converge to the ionization potential, as can be seen from the peak positions, shown with marks of different colours above the spectrum. In addition, three $6p7p$ perturber levels of series converging to the $6p_{3/2}$ limit were identified:

Level	Level energy (cm ⁻¹)
$6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_2$	57598.41
$6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$	58327.00
$6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$	58974.65

A closer look at the perturbed configurations is taken in Figure 3.7. The perturber levels displace neighboring levels with the same J . Therefore, the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ series is not perturbed by any perturber levels observed. Of the $6p11p$ configuration, two levels were identified, $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ and $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$. The $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ level is not observed. It is pushed to lower energies by interaction with the $6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_2$ perturber and falls outside of the scanned range. Ding et al. give this level's energy as $57\,261.4\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [43].

In the $6p12p$ configuration, $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ is pushed to slightly lower energies by $6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$, while $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ is influenced by $6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ and is also shifted towards lower energies. The order of the levels changes.

For the $6p13p$ configuration, a single level of an additional series, $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_1$ at 58368.89 cm^{-1} , was also observed. It probably emerges due to the close laying $6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ perturber level. This perturber also shifts $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ to higher energies and the order of the levels changes again. The $6p14p$ configuration has the same order as the preceding configuration. In $6p15p$, the $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ and $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ levels overlap due to the latter's interaction with the $6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ perturber. Starting with the $6p16p$ configuration, the level order is $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$, $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$, $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$. For each n , the $6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ levels are located in energy closely above the $6p(n+3)p$ configurations. The perturbing levels can be also seen as poles in the quantum defects shown in Figure 3.9. The given level assignments are taken from [39].

A more rigorous analysis of these perturbations can be done by the use of multichannel quantum defect theory, introduced by Seaton [44], Lu and Fano [45], and Cooke and Cromer [46], and applied to the Rydberg series of lead by Ding et al. [43], Farooqi et al. [39] and Hasegawa et al. [47, 48].

Figure 3.7: The perturbed levels in the lower part of the Rydberg spectrum of lead. Note how the perturber levels, marked with stars, displace neighboring levels with same J . This leads to a variable order of the levels in the $6pn_p$ configurations for different n .

With higher n , first the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ levels and later the $6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ and $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ levels disappear in the lines of the more prominent $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_3$ series, as is shown in the two spectra in Figure 3.8. The $6p23p$ and $6p20f$ configurations, expected around $59\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, are fully missing for unknown reasons in the scan with a heating current of 65 A. Slight variance in lead evaporation would explain this behavior. These missing levels were observed in a later conducted scan with a higher heating current of 160 A, which corresponds to a crucible temperature of about 1800 K. In this scan, the expected behavior of the line strengths to be proportional to n^{*-3} , as described by Fano [49], can be seen at high n . The different x-axes for the two spectra are due to the used ion counting mode in the higher temperature scan as opposed to the analog amplifier in the scan at lower temperature.

Figure 3.8: Two spectra of the even parity high Rydberg levels of lead. With higher n , first the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ levels and later the $6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ and $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ levels disappear in the lines of the more prominent $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_3$ series. The $6p23p$ and $6p20f$ configurations, expected around $59\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, are missing in the scan with a heating current of 65 A for unknown reasons. The different x-axes for the two spectra are due to the used ion counting mode in the higher temperature scan as opposed to the analog amplifier in the scan at lower temperature

The energies of the Rydberg levels and their quantum defects can be found in tables at the end of this chapter. All measured Rydberg levels have an empirical energy uncertainty of 0.15 cm^{-1} . This was determined by comparing measured level energies with the values of the NIST database for Rydberg scans conducted on several other elements with the same experimental setup in the past [42].

To calculate the ionization potential, a global fit of the Rydberg formula to the level energies of the four series was conducted. For that, the MultiNonlinearModelFit package [50] of the Wolfram Function Repository was used with Wolfram Mathematica 11.2, with which multiple fits to different data sets can be conducted simultaneously with a shared

fit parameter, in this case the $6p_{1/2}$ ionization potential. For the fit of the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ series, the Ritz expansion of the quantum defect was used up to the fourth order term, to account for its noticeable dependence on the principal quantum number n at lower energies. This can be also seen in the Lu-Fano plot in Figure 3.9. As already discussed, the lower levels of the other Rydberg series are prominently perturbed by the perturber levels. Therefore, the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ levels for $n < 16$, the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ levels for $n < 25$ and the $6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_1$ levels for $n < 18$ were excluded in the calculation of the ionization potential. With this method, the ionization potential of Pb I was calculated to

$$IP = 59819.54(4)_{\text{stat}}(4)_{\text{sys}} \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

which is in good agreement with the IP value of $(59819.558 \pm 0.003) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ given in the NIST database [38]. The systematical energy uncertainty is 0.04 cm^{-1} , due to the absolute wavelength accuracy of the used wavemeter.¹⁰ The calculated IP was used to calculate the quantum defects of the observed Rydberg levels which are given in the Lu-Fano plots and tables of this section. The value for the ionization potential given in the ionization schemes of this work is the one taken from the NIST database. The most efficient two step ionization scheme was found to be through the $6p17p(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ Rydberg level with a peak height of 4.64 in arbitrary units.

Rydberg series	Quantum defect
$6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$	$\delta_0 = 4.310(2), a = -1.74(21), b = 41(7)$
$6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$	$\delta = 4.234(1)$
$6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$	$\delta = 4.197(4)$
$6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_1$	$\delta = 1.027(3)$
Shared parameter: $IP = 59819.54(4)_{\text{stat}}(4)_{\text{sys}} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	

Table 3.1: Fit parameters of the Rydberg formula fitted globally to the unperturbed parts of the four observed Rydberg series. For the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ series, the Ritz expansion of the quantum defect up to the fourth order was used to account for its decrease at low n , shown in Figure 3.9. The IP from this fit was used to calculate the quantum defects of the observed Rydberg levels.

¹⁰High Finesse Angstrom WS/6 wavemeter, 600 MHz absolute accuracy

Lu-Fano plot of the even Rydberg series of Pb I

Figure 3.9: Lu-Fano plot of the observed even Rydberg series of lead. All quantum defects in this figure are calculated with the fitted IP value of $59819.54(4)_{\text{stat}}(4)_{\text{sys}} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The quantum defect of the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ Rydberg levels increases with increasing principal quantum number n at low n , but levels out for higher n . This behavior agrees well with the fitted quantum defect with correction from the fourth order Ritz expansion. In the lower parts of the three other Rydberg series, the quantum defect varies strongly with n due to the interaction with the indicated perturber levels. For high principal quantum numbers, the quantum defect does not show any in- or decreasing tendency in any of the series, which indicates a good fit of the calculated IP.

The Lu-Fano plot in Figure 3.9 shows that for low principal quantum number n the quantum defect δ of the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ Rydberg series depends on n . This is due to only partial shielding of the Rydberg electron from interaction with the nucleus by the electron core for low n . For higher n , δ levels out and becomes nearly constant. This is the expected behavior, as the distance of the Rydberg electron to rest of the electrons and the nucleus increases. The influence of the perturber levels on the series with $J = 1, 2$ can also be seen for lower n . For high n , the quantum defect is approximately constant for all series, indicating a good fit of the calculated IP.

A scan of the second excitation step from the ionization potential to higher energies down to a wavelength of 353 nm was conducted without the additional 532 nm laser light for nonresonant ionization. To account for the missing heating from that laser, the ion source heating current was increased to 75 A. No autoionizing levels were found in this scan.

Figure 3.10 shows the level energies and Rydberg fit of the observed even parity Rydberg series of lead. The fit residuals of the different series are also shown. Out of all fit residuals, only five have a magnitude of more than 0.2 cm, which is another sign of the quality of the fit.

Figure 3.10: Measured level energies and Rydberg fit of the observed even parity Rydberg series of lead. The fit residuals of the different series are also shown.

$6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$			$6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$		
n	Level energy [cm^{-1}]	Quantum defect δ	n	Level energy [cm^{-1}]	Quantum defect δ
11	57380.82	4.292(1)	11	57429.52	4.224(1)
12	57971.98	4.293(1)	12	57997.45	4.239(1)
13	58371.66	4.294(1)	13	58407.71	4.184(1)
14	58654.18	4.296(1)	14	58669.59	4.231(1)
15	58861.71	4.296(1)	15	58872.77	4.234(1)
16	59017.88	4.300(2)	16	59026.81	4.234(2)
17	59138.98	4.302(2)	17	59146.10	4.235(2)
18	59234.51	4.304(2)	18	59240.47	4.234(2)
19	59311.49	4.303(3)	22	59472.14	4.227(4)
20	59374.08	4.305(3)	24	59538.76	4.231(6)
21	59425.82	4.305(4)	25	59565.08	4.237(7)
22	59469.07	4.305(4)			
24	59536.46	4.311(6)			
25	59563.19	4.310(7)			
26	59586.27	4.310(8)			
27	59606.38	4.310(9)			
28	59623.99	4.311(10)			
29	59639.47	4.314(11)			
30	59653.36	4.303(12)			
31	59665.46	4.313(14)			
32	59676.44	4.308(15)			
33	59686.28	4.303(17)			
34	59695.01	4.314(19)			
35	59703.15	4.294(21)			

Figure 3.11: Observed levels of the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_0$ and $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_1$ Rydberg series of lead.

$6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$			$6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$		
n	Level energy [cm^{-1}]	Quantum defect δ	n	Level energy [cm^{-1}]	Quantum defect δ
12	58012.78	4.207(1)	8	57497.50	1.125(1)
13	58394.20	4.226(1)	9	58093.52	1.026(1)
14	58666.50	4.244(1)	10	58454.26	1.035(1)
15	58861.71	4.296(1)	11	58712.96	1.042(1)
16	59042.25	4.118(2)	12	58903.65	1.054(1)
17	59152.87	4.170(2)	13	59060.16	0.979(2)
18	59244.48	4.186(2)	14	59168.31	1.019(2)
19	59319.21	4.190(3)	15	59257.51	1.027(2)
20	59380.29	4.194(3)	16	59330.10	1.026(3)
21	59430.88	4.197(4)	18	59438.63	1.027(4)
22	59473.30	4.197(4)	19	59479.91	1.025(5)
24	59539.64	4.199(6)	21	59544.38	1.030(6)
25	59565.88	4.200(7)	22	59569.96	1.031(7)
26	59588.70	4.197(8)	23	59592.29	1.025(8)
27	59608.46	4.199(9)	24	59611.54	1.031(9)
28	59625.85	4.197(10)	25	59628.61	1.026(10)
29	59641.03	4.206(11)	26	59643.49	1.033(11)
30	59654.85	4.187(13)	27	59657.11	1.008(13)
31	59666.82	4.195(14)	28	59668.73	1.025(14)
32	59677.61	4.194(16)	29	59679.30	1.027(16)
33	59687.28	4.195(17)	30	59688.89	1.018(18)
34	59696.09	4.186(19)	31	59697.43	1.022(20)
35	59703.87	4.199(21)			
36	59711.19	4.176(23)			
37	59717.53	4.201(25)			
38	59723.72	4.158(28)			
39	59729.03	4.180(30)			
40	59733.98	4.187(33)			
41	59738.40	4.223(36)			
42	59742.81	4.182(39)			
43	59746.66	4.197(42)			
44	59750.26	4.202(45)			
45	59753.39	4.270(48)			
46	59756.79	4.180(52)			
47	59759.57	4.224(56)			
48	59762.24	4.238(60)			
49	59764.85	4.206(64)			
50	59767.27	4.180(68)			
51	59769.35	4.240(73)			
52	59771.50	4.206(78)			
53	59773.46	4.201(83)			
54	59775.39	4.146(88)			

Figure 3.12: Observed levels of the $6pnp(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2})_2$ and $6pnf(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ Rydberg series of lead.

3.3 Spectroscopy of the Odd Parity Autoionizing Levels of Lead

Bhatti et al. measured the $6p_{3/2}ns, nd, J = 1, 2, 3$ series of autoionizing (AI) levels between the $6p_{1/2}$ and $6p_{3/2}$ limit with three step photoionization via the $6p7s(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_1^{\circ}$ level and the $6p7p$ levels, three of which were identified in the spectrum in Figure 3.6 [14]. Nawaz et al. measured the same autoionizing series with different second intermediate levels, $6p7,8f(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ [41]. The $6p8f(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ level is also shown in Figure 3.6 at 57497.50 cm^{-1} . The $6p11s\frac{3}{2}[\frac{3}{2}]_2^{\circ}$ autoionizing level is shown as a very prominent peak at 70994.6 cm^{-1} in [41]. They also write about the $6p10s\frac{3}{2}[\frac{3}{2}]_2^{\circ}$ autoionizing level, but do not give the energy of it.

The wavelength needed to reach the energy region of these levels from the $6p8f(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ level or the $6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_2$ level are well in the TiSa laser's fundamental range.

For this work, the $6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_2$ perturber level at 57598.41 cm^{-1} , was used. The complete excitation scheme is shown in Figure 3.13. Due to the limited time, a spectrum via the $6p8f(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ level has not been taken.

Figure 3.13: Excitation scheme used for the three step laser ionization of lead. The first and second excitation step are the same as in [41].

The laser setup is schematically shown in Figure 3.14. The first excitation step remains the same as in section 3.2 with a tripled BRF tuned TiSa laser at 283.389 nm. For the second excitation step, a BRF tuned TiSa with intracavity doubling at 448.203 nm was used. The

scanning was again conducted with the grating tuned TiSa laser. Unlike in section 3.2, no external doubling of the scanning laser was needed and the beam lock system was not used. Again, all beams were expanded, superimposed and focused into the ion source. The laser powers were 15 mW for the first excitation step, 400 mW for the second step and 0.6 – 1.2 W for the final step into the AI, depending on the wavelength.

Figure 3.14: Schematic drawing of the laser setup for the three step ionization of lead. The first step is set up as already described in section 3.2. As second step, the light of an intracavity doubled BRF tuned TiSa laser at 448.203 nm was used. Scanning through the autoionizing levels was done with the fundamental of the grating tuned TiSa laser. All beams were expanded with telescopes, overlapped and then focused into the ionizer tube of the LIS STAND.

The same sample as in section 3.2 was used, the heating current of the crucible was set to 75 A and the ion current gain was 10^8 .

The scan was again done in several parts, which were joint together and and height corrected by their shared peaks in the overlapping regions. The result is shown in Figure 3.15.

AI levels of different series were observed with a wide variety of line shapes, peak heights and linewidths. The peak position of the asymmetric peaks has been determined by fitting Fano profiles to them, the narrow lines were fitted well with Gauss profiles. The prominent peaks from Nawaz et al. [41], $6p10,11s\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{3}{2} \right]_2^{\circ}$ are the second and third highest peaks in the presented spectrum, with heights of 6.7 and 5.0 in arbitrary units, respectively. The most prominent line is that of the $6p9d\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{5}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$ level with a height of 7.3. Since the gain used in this measurement was 10^8 opposed to 10^9 in section 3.2, this is the most efficient ionization scheme found, assuming the crucible temperatures at 75 A heating current and 65 A of heating current with added 6.5 W of 532 nm are somewhat comparable. The whole scheme is shown in Figure 3.17.

Figure 3.15: Three step ionization spectrum of lead excited from the $6p7p\left(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right)_2^{\circ}$ level. A total of 29 autoionizing states were observed. Their energies are collected in Table 3.2. The assignments were taken from [51]. The highest peak and therefore the most efficient ionization is into the $6p9d\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{5}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$ level at $70\,548.7\text{ cm}^{-1}$

The observed $6pnd$ configurations consist of five peaks: $\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{5}{2} \right]_{2,3}^{\circ}$, $\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{3}{2} \right]_{2,1}^{\circ}$ and $\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{7}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$. For $n = 8$, $\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{5}{2} \right]_{2,3}^{\circ}$ are well separated and symmetric. $\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{3}{2} \right]_{2,1}^{\circ}$ are symmetric and overlap strongly. $\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{7}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$ has an asymmetrical shape. With higher principal quantum number n , the $6pnd \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{5}{2} \right]_{2,3}^{\circ}$ levels overlap more. Also, the $6pnd \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{7}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$ starts to overlap with the $6pnd \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{3}{2} \right]_{2,1}^{\circ}$. The two sharp lines of the $6png$ configurations are well separated. The two peaks of the $6pns$ configurations, the symmetrical $\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{3}{2} \right]_2^{\circ}$ and the asymmetrical $\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{3}{2} \right]_1^{\circ}$, stay separated throughout the observed spectrum. The quantum defects of the observed AI series, given in Table 3.2, are in agreement with those given by Bhatti et al. in [51]. The peak at $69\,523.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was assigned to the $6p5g \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{7}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$ level, which is contrary to the energy of $69\,506.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, given in [52]. At that energy, no peak was found. For all series, the respective peak between $69\,700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $70\,900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was the strongest observed. In an unperturbed series, the product of the linewidth and the cube of the effective quantum number Γn^{*3} is supposed to be constant [23]. These normalized widths are given in the last column of Table 3.2. The values along each series are in the same order of magnitude.

In the lower energy region of the spectrum, periodic variation of the ion current is observed. This is most likely due to the variation of the grating laser power during the scan. Because of this variation, it is not possible to determine the linewidth of the $6p8d \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{7}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$ level. Furthermore, the linewidths of levels of the $6png$ configurations are in the order of the laser linewidth and can not be determined precisely, since the laser linewidth is not constant during scanning [28].

The two highest peaks of the observed spectrum, $6p9d \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{5}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$ and $6p10s \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{3}{2} \right]_2^{\circ}$, show an unusual line shape of a sharp peak on top of a broader base. They were fitted with sums of Gauss profiles to determine their position, but the origin of this shape is yet to be understood. Due to this shape, the linewidth of these two levels is not easily determined. In Figure 3.16, the fit of the $6p9d \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{5}{2} \right]_3^{\circ}$ level is shown. The narrow peak that sits on top of the base has a FWHM of $\sim 2.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is about 75 GHz. With that, ionization through this AI will be insensitive to small wavelength drifts of the ionization step, which ensures a stable ion current in on-line applications.

Three step ionization spectrum of Pb I via the $6p7p(3/2,1/2)_2^{\circ}$ level

Figure 3.16: Detail of the $6p9d\frac{3}{2}[\frac{5}{2}]_2^{\circ}$ and $6p9d\frac{3}{2}[\frac{5}{2}]_3^{\circ}$ Al levels. The shape of the peak at $70\,548.7\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is best fitted with the sum of two Gaussians. Why this shape arises is still to be found out.

The energy uncertainty of the observed Al levels is 0.4 cm^{-1} , as shown in previous experiments [22]. This is larger than for Rydberg levels due to the complicated shape variation of the resonances and because of the overlapping of many of the recorded peaks.

Calculation of the $6p_{3/2}$ limit of lead to a reasonable uncertainty was not possible with only two or three lines per series and was therefore not conducted.

Assignment	n	Level energy [cm^{-1}]	Quantum defect δ	FWHM cm^{-1}	Γn^3
$6pnd\frac{3}{2} [\frac{5}{2}]_2^\circ$	8	68926.8	3.30	13.4	14×10^2
	9	70513.7	3.31	19.6	36×10^2
	10	71445.5	3.31	18.0	54×10^2
$6pnd\frac{3}{2} [\frac{5}{2}]_3^\circ$	8	68993.6	3.27	11.7	12×10^2
	9	70548.7	3.28	-	-
	10	71466.6	3.29	10.1	31×10^2
$6pnd\frac{3}{2} [\frac{3}{2}]_2^\circ$	8	69163.8	3.19	63	70×10^2
	9	70648.2	3.19	47	93×10^2
	10	71527.3	3.20	24	76×10^2
$6pnd\frac{3}{2} [\frac{3}{2}]_1^\circ$	8	69180.7	3.18	16.2	18×10^2
	9	70667.1	3.18	18.7	37×10^2
	10	71543.0	3.18	6.3	20×10^2
$6pnd\frac{3}{2} [\frac{7}{2}]_3^\circ$	8	69340.4	3.10	-	-
	9	70774.5	3.08	87	18×10^3
	10	71616.4	3.07	35	12×10^3
$6png\frac{3}{2} [\frac{5}{2}]_{2,3}^\circ$	5	69484.4	0.02	-	-
	6	70836.0	0.02	-	-
	7	71650.5	0.02	-	-
$6png\frac{3}{2} [\frac{7}{2}]_3^\circ$	5	69523.1	-0.01	-	-
	6	70858.2	-0.01	-	-
	7	71664.3	-0.01	-	-
$6pns\frac{3}{2} [\frac{3}{2}]_2^\circ$	10	69750.0	4.86	-	-
	11	70995.1	4.85	2.30	53×10^1
	12	71752.8	4.85	1.4	51×10^1
$6pns\frac{3}{2} [\frac{3}{2}]_1^\circ$	10	69850.3	4.80	59	84×10^2
	11	71059.0	4.79	30.0	72×10^2

Table 3.2: Observed autoionizing levels of lead. For the calculation of the quantum defects δ , the $6p_{3/2}$ limit of $73\,900.632\text{ cm}^{-1}$ from the NIST database was used [38].

Figure 3.17: The resonant laser ionization scheme of lead developed. This scheme is suitable for TiSa laser based laser ion sources.

To estimate how far the efficiency of the described scheme can be pushed, saturation measurements of the different excitation steps have been conducted, as shown in Figure 3.18. The first step shows saturation starting around 4 mW, the second step around 250 mW. This means both were well saturated during the acquisition of the spectrum. The ionization step shows close to linear behavior even at laser powers of 1.7 W. An increase in available laser power at the required wavelength of 772.195 nm should lead to a further increase in efficiency. As shown by Li et al. in [28], up to 1.9 W are possible for that wavelength with the TiSa lasers system at TRILIS.

Saturation measurement of the developed ionization scheme of Pb I

Figure 3.18: Saturation measurements of the different excitation steps of the resonant laser ionization scheme of lead.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

To provide the requested isotopes for different experiments at TRIUMF, efficient schemes for TiSa laser based resonant laser ionization are needed. To develop such a scheme for lead, laser resonance ionization spectroscopy was conducted. From the intermediate $6p7s(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_1^{\circ}$ level at $35\,287.225\text{ cm}^{-1}$, a scan of the energy region close beneath the $6p_{1/2}$ ionization potential showed four different series of even parity Rydberg levels. A fit of the level energies to the Rydberg formula gave an IP of $59819.54(4)_{\text{stat}}(4)_{\text{sys}}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is in good agreement with the IP value of $(59\,819.558 \pm 0.003)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ given in the NIST database [38]. Furthermore, three perturber levels were observed.

Choosing the $6p7p(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2})_2$ level at $57\,598.41\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as second intermediate level, a scan of the odd parity autoionizing levels was conducted. The highest found peak was that of the $6p9d\frac{3}{2}[\frac{5}{2}]_3^{\circ}$ AI level at $70\,548.7\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It showed an uncommon line shape which origin is still to be understood. The full ionization scheme through this level is shown in Figure 3.17. Saturation measurements of the different excitation steps were taken and shown in Figure 3.18. The first and second step excitation step start to saturate at around 4 mW and 250 mW, respectively. These output powers are easily achieved with TiSa laser system at hand. The ionization step shows close to linear behavior even at laser powers of 1.7 W.

Conducting another scan of the observed AI levels and determining their peak heights, but with $6p8f(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2})_2$ as second intermediate level, would give further insight in the efficiency of developed ionization scheme. Furthermore, looking into the line shapes of $6p9d\frac{3}{2}[\frac{5}{2}]_3^{\circ}$ and $6p10s\frac{3}{2}[\frac{3}{2}]_2^{\circ}$ in that scan might help understanding their origin. Finally, on-line yield measurements of different lead isotopes with the developed ionization scheme would be interesting to compare to the last yield measurements of lead with the FEBIAD ion source, taken in 2012 [53].

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